

A background image showing a group of people sitting at tables in a conference room, attending a webinar. They are looking towards the front of the room, some with laptops open.

POST WEBINAR REPORT

From Risk to Resilience: Navigating the Cybersecurity Solutions Marketplace

WEBINAR

29 January 2025

11:00 – 12:30 CET

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From Risk to Resilience: Navigating the Cybersecurity Solutions Marketplace

The NERO Cybersecurity Second Webinar was a virtual event held on 29 January 2025 (11:00–12:30), aimed at helping SMEs strengthen their cyber resilience. The webinar introduced four key cybersecurity and privacy marketplaces—**NERO**, **CyberSuite**, **CyberSynchrony**, and **CyberSecPro**—designed to connect SMEs with tailored security solutions and expert insights. Focused on showcasing practical tools, fostering a security-first culture, and promoting collaboration between solution providers and adopters, the event provided valuable resources for SMEs looking to enhance their cybersecurity strategies.

SPEAKERS

Kitty Kioskli

NERO Project Coordinator
CEO&Co-founder, trustilio BV

Evangelos Ouzounis

Head of Capacity Building and
Skills, ENISA

Nefeli Bountouni

PM at Suite5 Data Intelligence
Solutions - CyberSuite
Marketplace and CyberSuite
MVP leader

Violeta Vasileva

CYberSynchrony Project
Coordinator, Gruppo Maggioli

Christos Douligeris

CyberSecPro Technical
Coordinator, UPRC

Marialetizia Mari

Trust-It Project Manager,
Webinar Moderator

This webinar highlighted insights and solutions from our key speakers:

- ☐☐ **Marialetizia Mari**, Trust-It Services
- ☐☐ **Evangelos Ouzounis**, ENISA
- ☐☐ **Kitty Kioskli**, trustilio BV
- ☐☐ **Nefeli Bountouni**, SUITE5 Data Intelligence Solutions Ltd., CyberSuite
- ☐☐ **Violeta Vasileva** PhD, MAGGIOLI SPA, CyberSynchrony
- ☐☐ **Christos Douligeris**, CyberSecPro

Audience and Participation

Number of attendees: **59**

Stakeholder Groups

Gender of Participants

Countries Represented

Keynote speeches and highlights

ENISA – EVANGELOS OUZOUNIS

Evangelos underscored several pressing cybersecurity challenges, particularly within supply chains and open-source systems. He highlighted the increasing threat of DDoS attacks, pointing to Ukraine as a stark example where such attacks have targeted critical infrastructure. Phishing, he noted, continues to be one of the most persistent and dangerous cyber threats. For small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), cybersecurity remains a major concern, largely due to their limited resources, expertise, and awareness of cyber risks. Research shows that 85% of SMEs recognize cybersecurity as a critical issue, with social engineering and phishing among the most common threats they face. To strengthen SME resilience, Evangelos recommended adopting a cybersecurity maturity assessment (CMA) developed by ENISA, whose structured framework acts as a practical roadmap, helping SMEs set clear cybersecurity goals, allocate budgets more effectively, and enhance their defenses through education and training.

NERO PROJECT – KITTY KIOSKLI

Kitty introduced the NERO Project, which aims to enhance cybersecurity for SMEs by connecting them with innovative solutions and expertise. The project fosters a dynamic ecosystem to help businesses adopt cybersecurity tools and strengthen resilience. It focuses on market adoption of advanced solutions, integrating EU-funded research, and improving cybersecurity preparedness through auditing and knowledge-sharing. NERO unfolds in three phases: analyzing the cybersecurity landscape and SME needs, developing an ecosystem and marketplace for cybersecurity solutions, and integrating, demonstrating, and training SMEs on these tools. To validate its approach, NERO runs three industry-specific use cases: securing patient data in healthcare, strengthening supply chain resilience in transportation and logistics, and boosting financial security. Kitty also highlighted the NERO Marketplace, a platform showcasing cybersecurity solutions and providing SMEs with up-to-date tools and support. Ultimately, NERO contributes to European cybersecurity by strengthening defenses, supporting policy and standards, and building a resilient cybersecurity ecosystem.

CYBERSUITE PROJECT – NEFELI BOUNTOUNI

Nefeli shared details about the CyberSuite project, a Horizon initiative designed to provide SMEs with a comprehensive cybersecurity framework that simplifies the entire cybersecurity lifecycle—from design and configuration to deployment, monitoring and management. CyberSuite consolidates advanced security, privacy, and trustworthiness into a single, user-friendly platform, addressing a crucial market gap with an “easy-to-onboard” and “easy-to-deploy” cybersecurity services Framework accompanied by an intuitive Marketplace. The project integrates a range of innovative cybersecurity solutions, including enterprise-grade “Security-as-a-Service” security recommendations, network-based intrusion detection, and code analysis and pentesting functionalities to ensure trusted interoperability. It also offers tools for cyber range capabilities and advanced cybersecurity analytics. Covering the full DevOps lifecycle, from initial planning to deployment, operation, and continuous monitoring, CyberSuite ensures SMEs can effectively protect their software infrastructures from cyber threats while maintaining a streamlined and accessible cybersecurity approach.

CYBERSYNCHRONY PROJECT – VIOLETA VASILEVA

Violeta introduced the CyberSynchrony project, a holistic initiative that integrates advanced technologies to build a resilient cybersecurity infrastructure. By combining technological advancements, human expertise, and security-driven processes, the project fosters a strong security culture while emphasizing rapid incident response to enhance preparedness and mutual assistance against cyber threats. CyberSynchrony is structured in three phases, with the team currently focused on the first, addressing key use cases to strengthen cyber resilience. The project operates within a dynamic ecosystem, offering specialised cybersecurity modules tailored to different needs. Its four core modules cover resilience and incident response, cross-border cyber cooperation, cyber threat intelligence with risk analysis, and proactive risk monitoring. Additionally, two broader modules address governance and compliance, aligning with regulations, and cybersecurity education, enhancing awareness and skills. This comprehensive approach ensures a flexible, adaptive, and robust cybersecurity framework.

CYBERSECPRO PROJECT – CHRISTOS DOULIGERIS

Christos presented the CyberSecPro Project, which aims to enhance the role of higher education institutions (HEIs) in providing hands-on cybersecurity skills to support digital transformation in critical sectors, particularly maritime. The project establishes a Learning Factory, bridging academia, industry, and SMEs to align cybersecurity education with real-world needs. CyberSecPro fosters collaboration between HEIs and private security companies, ensuring training meets industry demands, and key objectives include analysing cybersecurity skill gaps, establishing public-private partnerships for sustainable training, and integrating advanced technological tools. The project also refines existing training modules through an online Curricula Management System and strengthens ties with technology providers. Focusing on maritime cybersecurity, CyberSecPro addresses growing risks in the sector's digitalization. By equipping professionals with essential skills, the initiative enhances cybersecurity resilience, protecting assets and ensuring the smooth operation of global trade.

Panel Session

The audience expressed interest in understanding the key cybersecurity challenges SMEs face today, especially given the critical role digital presence plays in daily life. The moderator highlighted a question asking for insights into the most significant cybersecurity threats SMEs encounter from various perspectives. Additionally, the moderator sought to compare these challenges with the solutions provided by cybersecurity marketplaces, asking how these platforms address the specific security needs of SMEs and ensure they have the tools and support needed to strengthen resilience against cyber threats.

KITTY KIOSKLI

Kitty highlighted the cybersecurity challenges SMEs face, such as limited resources, lack of expertise, and the rising threat of ransomware and supply chain attacks. She explained that the NERO marketplace addresses these issues by providing cost-effective, scalable, and easy-to-deploy security solutions tailored for SMEs. The

platform simplifies access to trusted tools and services, integrating automation, compliance support, and expert guidance. This enables businesses to manage risks proactively and strengthen their cybersecurity posture without requiring deep technical expertise.

CHRISTOS DOULIGERIS

Christos emphasised that while affordability is important, usability and time efficiency are even more crucial when offering cybersecurity solutions to SMEs. He noted that despite the growing need for cybersecurity awareness, attracting SMEs to educational events remains a challenge. For example, while thousands may be expected to attend a webinar, actual participation often falls short, requiring significant effort to boost engagement. Christos stressed the need to explore new, more effective ways to encourage SMEs to actively engage with cybersecurity resources.

EVANGELOS OUZOUNIS

Evangelos highlighted that many SMEs lack awareness of cybersecurity risks, often believing it won't affect them or not fully understanding the business consequences. Nefeli stressed that cybersecurity is not just a technical issue, but a business risk. A ransomware attack, for example, can make critical business data inaccessible, crippling the company. Moreover, failing to meet legal requirements can lead to severe penalties. The key is for SMEs to recognise these risks, as understanding the problem is the first crucial step.

VIOLETA VASILEVA

Violeta noted that while SMEs are a primary focus, public institutions also face significant cybersecurity challenges, often with even fewer resources. The CyberSynchrony project includes use cases for both public administration and healthcare. Public sector workers often receive role-based training, neglecting technical aspects and cyber hygiene. Therefore, educational activities are crucial. However, engaging public sector employees can be challenging, as many are focused on specialized tasks and struggle to participate in activities like webinars. Addressing these issues is key to broader cybersecurity efforts.

NEFELI BOUNTOUNI

In response to a question about promoting marketplace adoption among SMEs, Nefeli explained that the CyberSuite project will host hackathons targeting students, universities, SMEs, and companies to familiarize them with the services. A second hackathon will invite security service developers to upload their offerings, increasing visibility and access to potential customers. Additionally, the CyberSuite Academy will provide training materials and courses for students and others. Nefeli emphasized that these activities, alongside long-term sustainability planning, are key to the CyberSuite Framework's and Marketplace's continued success.

Key takeaways – Quotations

“The mission of NERO is to foster a security first culture by raising awareness, educating employees and equipping SMEs to respond effectively to risks. This ensures SMEs can embrace digital transformation securely and sustainably” – Kitty Kioskli

“Modern healthcare is trained by potential cyber-attacks impacting patient care and exposing the inadequacies of current security solutions. There is an urgent need for strengthening digital security measures” – Violeta Vasileva

“Cybersecurity is not a single dimensional problem science. It’s a financial environment. I think that people who work in cyber security realize that it’s not very effective to work only on deeper theory” – Christos Douligeris

 Keywords: #Cybersecurity #SMEs #Resilience

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 <https://zenodo.org/records/14771571>

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